

DNA methylation signatures identify biologically distinct thyroid cancer subtypes

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ABSTRACT

The global patterns of aberrant DNA methylation in thyroid cancer are not known. In this study, we have used DNA methylation arrays to determine, for the first time, the genome-wide promoter methylation status of papillary, follicular, medullary and anaplastic thyroid tumors. We identified 262 and 352 hyper and 13 and 21 hypomethylated genes in differentiated papillary and follicular tumors respectively. Surprisingly, undifferentiated tumors displayed more hypomethylated genes (280 in anaplastic and 393 in medullary tumors) than aberrantly hypermethylated genes (86 in anaplastic and 131 in medullary tumors). Hypermethylated genes in tumors originating from follicular cells were preferentially involved in developmental processes whilst those in medullary tumors were primarily involved in cell signaling and iodine pathways. Hypomethylated genes were enriched in immune system functions. Among the genes identified, we show that four potential tumor suppressor genes (*ADAMTS8*, *HOXB4*, *ZIC1*, and *KISS1R*) and four potential oncogenes (*INSL4*, *DPPA2*, *TCL1B*, and *NOTCH4*) are frequently regulated by aberrant methylation in primary thyroid tumors. Further studies are needed to determine the potential clinical interest of the tumor subtype-specific DNA methylation signatures described herein and the role of aberrant promoter hypomethylation in undifferentiated thyroid tumors.

INTRODUCTION

Thyroid cancer is the most frequent malignant neoplasm in the endocrine system. According to their histopathological characteristics, thyroid tumors are classified as differentiated or undifferentiated cancers. Differentiated tumors are subdivided into papillary thyroid cancer (PTC) and follicular thyroid cancer (FTC). Undifferentiated tumors include two main subtypes: anaplastic thyroid cancer (ATC) and medullary thyroid carcinoma (MTC). PTCs and FTCs often have a good prognosis when identified in the early stages of the disease. In contrast, ATC represents the most aggressive and undifferentiated subtype of thyroid cancer, responds poorly to treatment and is associated with the worst prognosis due to the generally invasive local growth and distant metastasis (lungs) (1). Thyroid malignancies are mainly derived from follicular cells; PTC, FTC and ATC together constitute 95% of thyroid cancers with the papillary variant representing 80-85% of the total. In contrast, parafollicular C cells develop MTCs, whose incidence accounts for 3-12% of thyroid cancers. Factors involved in the etiology of thyroid cancer include radiation exposure or iodine deficient diets (2) but the underlying molecular mechanisms are still largely unknown.

Thyroid tumors have been shown to present many genetic alterations. Examples include germ line mutations at the protein kinase, cAMP-dependent, regulatory, type I, alpha (*PRKARIA*) and somatic mutations involved in the activation of oncogenes such as the v-raf murine sarcoma viral oncogene homolog B1 (*BRAF*) and the RAS family (3) or in the inactivation of tumor suppressor genes such as the phosphatase and tensin homolog (*PTEN*) and the tumor protein p53 (*TP53*) (4). Interestingly, rearrangements at the "rearranged during transfection" protooncogene (*RET*) are frequent in both familial and sporadic thyroid tumors (5, 6). Besides genetic mistakes, recent research has demonstrated that epigenetic alterations might also play an essential role in thyroid cancer. For example, the thyroid-specific genes solute carrier family 5 (sodium iodide symporter), member 5 (*SLC5A5*) and thyroid-stimulating hormone receptor (*THSR*) have been shown to be frequently repressed by aberrant DNA promoter hypermethylation in thyroid cancer (7-9). It is worth mentioning that, as both genes play an important role in iodine uptake, it has been proposed that tumors displaying aberrant hypermethylation at their gene promoters could be good candidates for receiving

demethylating agents in conjunction with TSH-promoted radioiodine therapy (9). Other examples of genes frequently hypermethylated in thyroid cancer include the apoptosis-related cysteine protease (*CASP8*) (10), the tissue inhibitor of metalloprotease 3 (*TIMP3*) (11, 12), the ataxia telangiectasia mutated gene (*ATM*) (7) and RAS association domain family protein 1 (*RASSF1*) (13).

Although the aberrant methylation status of a number of candidate genes in specific thyroid cancer subtypes are well characterized, the genome-wide promoter DNA methylation patterns of thyroid cancer are still unknown. To address this issue, we used 27 K Infinium Methylation Arrays to analyze the methylation status of healthy thyroid tissues, thyroid cancer cell lines and primary PTCs, FTCs, ATC, and MTCs. Results identified tumor subtype-specific promoter DNA methylation signatures with potential as clinical predictors.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Human tissue samples.

We analyzed a cohort of 54 snap frozen thyroid samples, part of which were obtained from the Tumor Bank at the Institute of Oncology of Asturias (Asturias, Spain), part from the Pathology and Otolaryngology departments at the Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias (Asturias, Spain) and the remainder from the Hereditary Endocrine Cancer Group (Spanish National Cancer Research Centre, CNIO). The samples consisted in 13 papillary thyroid primary tumors (PTC), 6 follicular thyroid carcinomas, 11 anaplastic thyroid primary tumors (ATC), 20 medullary thyroid carcinomas and 4 normal thyroid samples. These latter 4 histologically normal thyroid sections were from goiter cases in patients with total or subtotal thyroidectomy. Diagnoses were evaluated by hematoxylin-eosin-stained slides of all samples according to the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria and the snap frozen tissues were stored at -80°C before isolation of the DNA. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee on Clinical Investigation of the Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias and all patients gave their consent.

Cell lines and Cell Culture

Human thyroid carcinoma-derived cell lines, K1 (Papillary Thyroid cancer), FTC-133 (Follicular thyroid carcinoma), 8305C (undifferentiated thyroid cancer) and TT (medullary thyroid carcinoma) were obtained from the European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC) and cultured according to the supplier's instructions. Briefly, cells were maintained in DEMEM (Gibco, Grand Island, NY, USA) supplemented with 10% by volume of fetal bovine serum, penicillin (100 u/ml) and streptomycin (100µg/ml) (Penstrep, (Gibco, Grand Island, NY, USA). Cells were maintained in a standard humidified incubator at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere.

DNA methylation profiling using bead arrays.

Microarray-based DNA methylation profiling was performed with the Illumina Infinium Human Methylation 27K Platform (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) on a total of 8 thyroid cancer

patient biopsies, four thyroid carcinoma cell lines and two normal thyroid samples as controls. Genomic DNA was extracted from the frozen primary tissues by proteinase K treatment followed by a standard phenol/chloroform procedure. Cultured cells were trypsinized, collected by centrifugation, washed with PBS (phosphate-buffered saline) and DNA was isolated with the same procedure.

This Infinium array allows the interrogation of 27,578 highly informative CpG sites per sample at single-nucleotide resolution for more than 14,000 genes. This 12-sample BeadChip features content derived from the NCBI CCDS database (Genome Build 36) and is supplemented with more than 1,000 cancer-related genes. The Infinium Methylation Assay accomplishes this high multiplexing by combining bisulphite conversion of genomic DNA and whole-genome amplification (WGA) sample preparation with direct, array-based capture and enzymatic scoring of the CpG loci. Bisulphite conversion of DNA was performed using the EZ DNA Methylation Kit (Zymo Research, Orange, CA) following the manufacturer's procedures, with the modifications described in the Infinium Assay Methylation Protocol Guide. Processed DNA samples were then hybridized to the BeadChip (Illumina). The assay interrogates the chemically differentiated loci using two site-specific probes, one designed for the methylated locus (M bead type) and another for the unmethylated locus (U bead type). Single-base extension of the probes incorporates a labeled ddNTP, which is subsequently stained with a fluorescence reagent. The methylation level for the interrogated locus is determined by calculating the ratio of the fluorescent signals from the methylated vs. unmethylated sites. The ratio of fluorescent signals is then computed from the two alleles according to the following formula: $\beta = [\text{Max}(M, 0)] / [\text{Max}(U, 0) + \text{Max}(M, 0) + 100]$. This beta value is a quantitative measure of DNA methylation levels of specific CpG sites, and ranges from 0 for completely unmethylated to 1 for completely methylated.

Before analyzing the array data, we excluded possible sources of technical and gender-specific influences. Every beta value in the array platform is accompanied by a detection p-value. Technical bias was minimized by excluding probes with detection p-values > 0.01. Gender-specific bias was avoided by excluding CpGs in sex chromosomes.

Hierarchical cluster analysis and definition of differentially methylated genes.

Hierarchical clustering was conducted in R (<http://www.r-project.org/>). Only the 26,239 autosomal CpG sites that met our quality criteria were used in the analysis.

As only two normal thyroid samples and two primary tumors of each thyroid subtype were available, we used strict criteria to define hyper- and hypomethylated genes. We initially defined a gene as unmethylated in normal samples when the CpG site had a beta value below 0.3 in both samples. Similarly, we defined a gene as methylated in normal samples when the CpG site had a beta value over 0.7 in both samples. A gene was classified as hypermethylated in a specific thyroid cancer subtype when it was unmethylated in normal samples and showed beta values greater than 0.2 (a more than 20% difference in methylation level) in both primary tumors compared to average beta values of normal tissues. Conversely, a gene was classified as hypomethylated in a specific thyroid cancer subtype when it was methylated in normal samples and showed beta values less than 0.2 (a more than 20% difference in methylation level) in both primary tumors compared to average beta values of normal tissues.

Computational gene expression analysis

We compared the methylation data (groups of differentially methylated genes) with available gene expression data from GEO (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo>). We selected a data base which included all the thyroid cancer subtypes in the study and normal thyroid samples as controls (GEO data base GSE27155) (14).

We identified differentially expressed genes by thyroid cancer subtype (t-test, $FDR < 0.05$), and compared the associations between hyper- and hypomethylated genes with gene expression. Additionally, Fisher's exact test was used to analyze preferential association between promoter hyper- or hypomethylation and changes in gene expression.

Gene ontology analysis of differentially methylated genes.

A/The hypergeometric test (Using GOstats to test gene lists for GO term association; (15) was used to determine enriched Gene Ontology terms within the selected methylation groups. We compared differentially methylated groups of genes against a background comprising all the genes in the Illumina Infinium array using a Fisher's exact test.

Proportions of PcG-marks and bivalent domains in different methylation groups

The presence of the PcG-marks and bivalent domains in the different methylation groups and all the genes included in the array were compared using a Fisher's exact test. A genome-wide map of Polycomb target genes and 3mK4H3/3mK27H3-enriched genes (bivalent histone domains) in embryonic stem cells (ESCs) is available as supplemental material in the articles by Lee et al and Pan et al, respectively (16, 17).

Bisulfite pyrosequencing.

Genomic DNA isolation was performed according to a standard phenol-chloroform extraction protocol. Bisulfite modification of DNA was performed with the EZ DNA Methylation-Gold kit (Zymo Research) following the manufacturer's instructions. The set of primers for PCR amplification and sequencing were designed using the specific software PyroMark assay design (version 2.0.01.15). Primer sequences were designed to hybridize with CpG free sites to ensure methylation-independent amplification (**Supplementary Table 1**). After PCR amplification of the region of interest with the specific primers, pyrosequencing was performed using PyroMark Q24 reagents, vacuum prep workstation, equipment and software (Qiagen).

Primary tumors were classified as hypermethylated when the gene promoter showed average methylation values above 0.2 (a difference in methylation level of over 20%) compared to average values for normal thyroid samples. Conversely, primary tumors were classified as hypomethylated when the gene promoter showed average methylation values below 0.2 (a difference in methylation level of over 20%) compared to average methylation values of normal thyroid samples.

Statistical analysis.

All data imports, processing and downstream analyses were conducted in R (version 2.15.0) (<http://www.r-project.org/>) and Bioconductor (version 2.9) (18). In general, all statistical tests were performed using a significance level of 0.05.

RESULTS

Genome-wide promoter DNA methylation profiling and differentially methylated genes in thyroid cancer

We compared the DNA methylation status of 27,578 sequences in 2 PTCs, 2 FTCs, 2 MTCs, 2 ATCs, 2 non-tumorigenic thyroid samples and 4 independently isolated human thyroid cancer cell lines (K1, FTC-133, 8305C and TT) using Illumina Infinium Methylation Arrays. As expected, the methylation status of 1063 CpG sites in 591 genes located in the X and Y chromosomes were perfectly correlated with gender (**Supplementary Fig. 1**). Unsupervised clustering of samples exclusively using the methylation signals of the autosomal probes (26239; 13789 genes) revealed two main clusters (**Fig. 1**): One cluster comprising the healthy tissues and the primary tumors and the other containing three of the four cancer cell lines (K1, FTC-133 and 8305C). Interestingly, papillary and follicular tumors sub-clustered together with healthy tissues and undifferentiated tumors were more similar to cancer cell lines than differentiated tumors (**Fig. 1**).

To identify differentially methylated genes in thyroid cancer we initially classified CpG sites according to their methylation status in healthy samples, and following the criteria described in the methodology we found that 2946 CpGs were unmethylated and 16901 were methylated. We then identified genes that were differentially methylated in each thyroid cancer subtype compared with normal tissues: 309 CpGs (corresponding to 262 genes) were hypermethylated in PTCs, 408 (352 genes) in FTCs, 148 (131 genes) in MTCs and 114 (86 genes) in ATCs (**Supplementary Table 2; Fig. 2A, 2B**). Of these, 184 CpG sites (corresponding to 155 genes) were hypermethylated only in PTC, 250 (210 genes) only in FTCs, 84 (73 genes) only in MTCs and 38 (24 genes) only in ATCs (**Supplementary. Table 3, Fig. 2B**). Similarly, these criteria allowed the identification of 14 (corresponding to 13 genes) hypomethylated probes in PTCs, 24 (21 genes) in FTCs, 490 (393 genes) in MTCs and 328 (280 genes) in ATCs (**Supplementary. Table 4; Fig. 2A, 2B**). Of these, 3 CpG sites (corresponding to 3 genes) were hypomethylated specifically in PTC (and in no other tissue), 10 (10 genes) in FTCs, 338 (261 genes) in MTCs and 174 (147 genes) in ATCs (**Supplementary. Table**

5, Fig. 2B). It is worth noting that the detailed examination of the CpG content of the sequences targeted by alterations of DNA methylation showed that hypermethylation occurred more frequently at CpG islands (77.2 %) whilst hypomethylation was more frequent at CpG poor regions (22.8%) (Fisher's exact test, $p < 0.001$) (**Fig. 2A**). However we did not find any statistically significant differences between hyper- and hypomethylated CpG sites with respect to their average distance to the transcription start site (TSS) (**Supplementary Fig. 2**).

Collectively, differentiated tumors (PTCs and FTCs) showed more hyper- than hypomethylated CpG sites (620 versus 37; Fisher's exact test, $p < 0.001$) whilst in undifferentiated tumors (MTC and ATC) the opposite was found: 243 CpG sites were hypermethylated vs. 672 hypomethylated (Fisher's exact test, $p < 0.001$) (**Fig. 2A, 2B**). Specific analysis of common hyper- and hypomethylated CpG sites in differentiated and undifferentiated primary tumors again showed that the location of these DNA methylation events differed: CpG dinucleotide hypermethylation mostly occurred at CpG islands, while CpG hypomethylation was present mainly in non-CpG-island genes (Fisher's exact test, $p < 0.001$) (**Fig. 2C**).

Relationship between promoter hyper- and hypomethylation and genome-wide expression

To determine the role of aberrant promoter methylation on gene expression, we compared our methylation data with the available expression data of normal thyroid tissue and that of primary tumors of each subtype (GEO data base GSE27155) (14). We first identified differentially expressed genes for each thyroid cancer subtype (t-test, $FDR < 0.05$), and compared the associations between hyper- and hypomethylated genes with gene expression (**Fig. 3**). We found that 7.5% of the genes hypermethylated in PTC, 1.5% in FTC, 7.3% in MTC, and 7.7% in ATC were down-regulated. Moreover, we found that 12.5% of the genes hypomethylated in PTC, 5.2% in MTC, and 3.2% in ATC were up-regulated (**Fig. 3**). We did not, however, find any association between hypomethylated genes in FTC and changes in gene expression. Furthermore, no preferential association between promoter hyper- or hypomethylation and changes in gene expression was found.

Gene ontology categories of hypermethylated and hypomethylated genes

We used Gene ontology (GO) to analyze the biological functions of the hypermethylated and hypomethylated genes in thyroid cancer subtypes. A list of significantly enriched GO terms is provided in **Tables 1 and 2** (Fisher's exact test, $p < 0.001$). Analysis of hypermethylated genes showed non-random distribution of GO terms in biological processes. These genes were mainly enriched for terms related to developmental processes, except in the case of medullary tumors which were primarily involved in cell signaling and iodine pathways (**Table 1**).

We also used the GO to investigate the biological functions of the hypomethylated genes (**Table 1**). We identified significant enrichment of specific GO terms in poorly differentiated thyroid tumors (MTC and ATC), whereas the analysis did not detect any enriched terms in differentiated tumors (PTC and FTC) (**Table 1**). MTC and ATC hypomethylated genes were enriched for gene ontology terms mainly associated with the immune system (**Table 1**).

Enrichment of PcG-marks and bivalent histone domains of aberrantly methylated genes in thyroid cancer

To study genomic features which provide clues about the mechanisms underlying the aberrant methylation changes in thyroid cancer we investigated whether the differentially methylated genes were among those targeted by the polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) (16) or bivalent histone domains (3mK4H3 + 3mK27H3) (17) in ESCs. As shown in **Figure 4**, compared with all the genes analyzed in the array, hypermethylated genes were highly enriched for loci targeted by PcG and bivalent histone marks in each thyroid cancer subtype (Fisher's exact test, $p < 0.001$) (**Fig. 4**). Conversely, hypomethylated genes showed a decrease in genes targeted by PcG and bivalent marks (**Fig. 4**).

Hypermethylated tumor suppressor candidate genes in differentiated primary tumors.

To further validate the results obtained with the methylation array for differentiated tumors we selected two hypermethylated genes found in PTC, *ADAMTS8* and *HOXB4*, and another two hypermethylated genes in FTC, *ZIC1* and *KISS1R* (**Fig. 5**). These selected genes have frequently been found hypermethylated, or been described as tumor suppressors, in other cancer types (19-22). We determined their promoter methylation profiles in 38 samples by bisulfite pyrosequencing. Results corroborated the methylation array data (**Fig. 5; Supplementary Fig. 3**). We detected hypermethylation at the *ADAMTS8* and *HOXB4* promoters in 4 of the 22 PTC tumors (18%), and hypermethylation at the *ZIC1* and *KISS1R* promoters in 4 and 1 of the 6 FTC tumors respectively (67% and 17%), confirming that this is a frequent event in vivo.

Hypomethylated candidate oncogenes in undifferentiated primary tumors.

To validate the results obtained with the methylation array for undifferentiated tumors we selected two genes found hypomethylated in MTC, *INSL4* and *DPPA2*, and another two genes hypomethylated in ATC, *TCL1B* and *NOTCH4* (**Fig. 6**). These selected genes have been described as potential oncogenes in other cancer types (23-26). We determined their promoter methylation profiles in 35 samples by bisulfite pyrosequencing. Results corroborated the methylation array data (**Supplementary Fig. 3**). We detected hypomethylation at the *INSL4* and *DPPA2* promoters in 12 and 6 of the 20 MTC tumors respectively (60% and 30%), and hypomethylation at the *TCL1B* and *NOTCH4* promoters in 7 and 5 of the 11 ATC tumors respectively (64% and 45%), evidencing the frequent occurrence of this event in vivo.

DISCUSSION

Although aberrant genomic DNA methylation is a hallmark of cancer (27) and the genome-wide aberrant promoter DNA methylation patterns of many tumor types has been meticulously described (28-30), data on aberrant DNA methylation in thyroid cancer is mainly restricted to single copy candidate genes in specific tumor subtypes (31-33). In this study, we used DNA methylation arrays to determine, for the first time, the genome-wide promoter methylation status of primary papillary, follicular, medullary and anaplastic thyroid tumors, non-tumorigenic thyroid tissues and four thyroid cancer cells lines. Using this approach, we identified 262 genes hypermethylated and 13 hypomethylated in papillary tumors, 352 hypermethylated and 21 hypomethylated in follicular tumors, 56 hypermethylated and 280 hypomethylated in anaplastic tumors and, 131 hypermethylated and 393 hypomethylated in medullary tumors. As in other tissue types (34), healthy samples, cancer cell lines and primary tumors presented specific DNA methylation signatures that permit their clustering within their corresponding category simply by noting their DNA methylation patterns. Papillary, follicular, medullary and anaplastic thyroid tumor subtypes, were also found to present specific DNA methylation signatures, which suggests that methylation profiling in thyroid cancer might be of clinical value in diagnosis, prognosis and prediction of response to therapies (35). As in previous studies using the similar methylation arrays (29, 30) differentiated papillary and follicular tumors showed many more hypermethylated (526) than hypomethylated (33) genes. In contrast, undifferentiated medullary and anaplastic tumors exhibited more hypomethylated than hypermethylated genes (546 versus 199).

The role of promoter hypomethylation in cancer is still largely unknown. Previous studies have shown that hepatocellular tumors display more hypomethylated than hypermethylated gene promoters (36-38). However, these studies focused their attention mainly in the aberrant hypermethylated promoters. In the case of thyroid cancer, promoter hypomethylation might be even more relevant because it is specifically enriched in undifferentiated medullary and anaplastic tumors. As undifferentiated thyroid tumors are more aggressive and present poorer prognosis than differentiated tumors, further studies should be undertaken to determine the specific role of aberrant

promoter hypomethylation in thyroid cancer. A functional role of promoter hypomethylation in cancer could also have clinical implications as demethylating drugs can reactivate some genes aberrantly hypomethylated in cancer cells (39): The possible negative effects of antitumor treatment with demethylating drugs on oncogene reactivation need to be determined in future studies.

The comparison of our methylation data with genome-wide gene expression data showed that the role of aberrant promoter methylation in thyroid cancer is complex. We found that regardless of methylation status, in non tumorigenic thyroid tissues, changes in DNA methylation do not necessarily involve changes in gene expression. This concurs with previous studies showing that changes in DNA methylation are not always associated with changes in gene expression both in healthy tissues (40) and cancer (41, 42). Further studies are required to determine the role of non-functional aberrant methylation in thyroid cancer.

Gene ontology analysis indicated that gene promoter hypermethylation and hypomethylation in thyroid tumors tend to target different biological processes. Hypermethylated genes were mainly found to be related to developmental process along the lines of/similar to those found in previous studies of other cancer types (43, 44). However, hypomethylated genes were enriched for gene ontology terms associated with the immune system. As this is associated with more aggressive tumors (MTC and ATC) further research is needed to clarify the role of the immune system in tumor progression in these subtypes of thyroid cancer.

We also confirmed previous observations that CpG hypermethylation events in cancer are significantly more likely to occur in the promoters of those genes with enriched Polycomb occupancy and the presence of bivalent histone domains in ESCs (34, 45-47). This might link thyroid cancer pathogenesis to stem cells, and suggests that thyroid tumors might originate from cells with stem-like features.

Using candidate gene approaches, recent works have identified a number of aberrantly methylated genes in thyroid cancer. For example, the cell cycle regulator p16 has been shown to be aberrantly hypermethylated in follicular and papillary thyroid tumors (48, 49). Other tumor suppressor genes frequently methylated in thyroid cancer are *RASFFIA* (32% PTCs, 100% FTCs, 40% MTCs

and 33% ATCs), *Rap1GAP* (72% PTCs and 38% FTCs), a GTPase activating protein that inhibits Rap1, and whose down regulation is related with tumor invasion (50, 51). *PTEN* gene, a negative modulator of the PI3K/AKT pathway that is constitutively activated in tumors, has been found hypermethylated in 50% of PTCs and in 100% of FTCs (52). Aberrant methylation of other tumor suppressor genes such as *TIMP3* (53% PTC), *SLC5A8* (33% PTC), *DAPK* (34% PTC), *RARβ2* (22% PTC) has been associated with mutation of the proto oncogene ***B-Raf*** (*BRAF*) (12). Interestingly, thyroid tumors have also been shown to present aberrant promoter hypermethylation at endocrine-related genes such as the solute carrier family 5 (sodium iodide symporter), member 5 (*SLC5A5*), and the thyroid-stimulating hormone receptor (*THSR*) has been shown to be frequently repressed by aberrant DNA promoter hypermethylation in thyroid cancer (7-9). Other examples of genes frequently hypermethylated in thyroid cancer include the apoptosis-related cysteine protease (*CASP8*) (10) and the ataxia telangiectasia mutated (*ATM*) (7). Several of these genes have also been identified in our study, which supports the reliability of our experimental design and confirms the notion that aberrant promoter methylation is a relevant molecular alteration in thyroid cancer.

Among the genes identified in our study, some have been previously shown to be oncogenic or to have tumor suppressor action in cancer. For example, the member of the ZIC family (C2H2-type zinc finger proteins) *ZIC1*, that we found to be frequently hypermethylated in FTCs, has also been shown to be a tumor suppressor gene frequently repressed by aberrant promoter hypermethylation in colorectal cancer (21). The other gene shown to be aberrantly hypermethylated in FTCs in our study, the galanin-like G protein-coupled receptor (*KISS1R* or *GPR54*) has been proposed as suppressing metastasis in melanoma and breast carcinoma (22). Moreover, *KISS1R* was found to be downregulated and to have a metastasis-suppressing role in follicular thyroid tumors (53); the tumor subtype in which we found this gene to be frequently hypermethylated. The two genes validated in papillary tumors, *HOXB4* and *ADAMTS8*, have also been proposed as possessing tumor suppressing activity in cancer (19, 54) that, in some cases is mediated by aberrant promoter hypermethylation (19, 20, 54-56). In undifferentiated thyroid tumors, we validated four genes that become aberrantly hypomethylated (*NOTCH4* and *TCL1B* in ATCs; and *INSL4* and *DPPA2* in MTCs). Interestingly,

these genes have long been muted to have an oncogenic role in cancer. *NOTCH4* is frequently overexpressed in thyroid tumors (57) and has been shown to promote metastasis in salivary adenoid cystic carcinomas (58). *TCL1* is an oncogene frequently activated by reciprocal translocations t(14;14)(q11;q32), t(7;14)(q35;q32) or inversion inv(14)(q11;q32) in leukemia (25). It was also identified as an alternative mechanism of activation in B-cell chronic lymphocytic leukemia mediated by promoter hypomethylation (59). Thus, hypomethylation-dependent oncogenic activation of *TCL1* might be a frequent event in cancer. *INSL4* and *DPPA2*, the two genes validated in MTCs, have also been reported to promote tumorigenesis in different types of cancer.

INSL4 (pro-EPIL) belongs to the insulin and insulin-like growth factors family and is expressed strongly during the first trimester of pregnancy by the differentiated syncytiotrophoblast (60). It has been shown to be overexpressed in breast tumors with aggressive an phenotype (23) but the underlying mechanisms are still unknown. The aberrant overexpression of *INSL4* in breast tumors, together with the aberrant promoter hypomethylation reported in this study suggest that promoter demethylation might be a frequent mechanism of activation of *INSL4* oncogene activation in cancer. *DPPA2* (Developmental pluripotency-associated 2) is expressed early in the embryo's development (61) but also in some tumor types (24). Although the underlying molecular mechanism has not been reported yet, our data indicate that promoter hypomethylation might play an important role. Collectively, these results suggest that aberrant promoter methylation is an important molecular mechanism underlying the aberrant regulation of tumor suppressor genes and oncogenes in thyroid cancer.

In conclusion, our methylation profiling in thyroid cancer shows that thyroid cancer subtypes present differential promoter methylation signatures and that undifferentiated subtypes are characterized by aberrant promoter hypomethylation rather than hypermethylation. Our results could have at least two types of clinical implications: The tumor subtype-specific DNA methylation signatures might be useful in diagnosis and/or prognosis, and the frequent promoter hypomethylation observed in undifferentiated tumors might be relevant for treatment with demethylating drugs.

Table 1. Gene ontology terms significantly enriched ($p < 0.001$) in the group of hypermethylated genes in each thyroid cancer subtype.

Biological process		
<i>Hypermethylated genes in PTC</i>		
GO term ID	Term	Pvalue
GO:0009653	anatomical structure morphogenesis	2.41E-08
GO:0048856	anatomical structure development	1.816E-07
GO:0048731	system development	4.245E-07
GO:0007275	multicellular organismal development	2.4869E-06
GO:0032502	developmental process	2.7195E-06
GO:0032501	multicellular organismal process	4.5593E-06
GO:0001501	skeletal system development	0.000009109
GO:0048736	appendage development	1.89096E-05
GO:0060173	limb development	1.89096E-05
GO:0072358	cardiovascular system development	2.28195E-05
GO:0072359	circulatory system development	2.28195E-05
GO:0009888	tissue development	3.12569E-05
GO:0048513	organ development	4.08076E-05
GO:0007399	nervous system development	5.83991E-05
GO:0007417	central nervous system development	5.99787E-05
<i>Hypermethylated genes in FTC</i>		
GO term ID	Term	Pvalue
GO:0048856	anatomical structure development	6.8E-09
GO:0032502	developmental process	1.3461E-06
GO:0048731	system development	0.00000225
GO:0048513	organ development	3.9017E-06
GO:0032501	multicellular organismal process	4.2116E-06
GO:0009653	anatomical structure morphogenesis	9.4452E-06
GO:0007275	multicellular organismal development	1.64454E-05
GO:0065007	biological regulation	7.33922E-05
GO:0050789	regulation of biological process	7.53384E-05
GO:0048518	positive regulation of biological process	0.000274753
GO:0048869	cellular developmental process	0.000379027
GO:0007399	nervous system development	0.000445126
<i>Hypermethylated genes in ATC</i>		
GO term ID	Term	Pvalue
GO:0007275	multicellular organismal development	5.09974E-05
GO:0032501	multicellular organismal process	0.000212912
GO:0048598	embryonic morphogenesis	0.000235041
GO:0001501	skeletal system development	0.000259368
GO:0007389	pattern specification process	0.000349484
GO:0060977	coronary vasculature morphogenesis	0.000444512
GO:0048731	system development	0.000475064
GO:0032502	developmental process	0.000566321
GO:2000021	regulation of ion homeostasis	0.000616644
GO:0060973	cell migration involved in heart development	0.000663847
GO:0061323	cell proliferation involved in heart morphogenesis	0.000663847
<i>Hypermethylated genes in MTC</i>		
GO term ID	Term	Pvalue
GO:0050865	regulation of cell activation	0.000234927
GO:0015705	iodide transport	0.000576894
GO:0042531	positive regulation of tyrosine phosphorylation of STAT protein	0.000635489

Table 2. Gene ontology terms significantly enriched ($p < 0.001$) in the group of hypomethylated genes in each thyroid cancer subtype.

Biological process		
<i>Hypomethylated genes in MTC</i>		
GO term ID	Term	Pvalue
GO:0050832	defense response to fungus	1.514E-07
GO:0031640	killing of cells of other organism	1.6598E-06
GO:0009620	response to fungus	5.4781E-06
GO:0051770	positive regulation of nitric-oxide synthase biosynthetic process	1.71576E-05
GO:0051767	nitric-oxide synthase biosynthetic process	5.91664E-05
GO:0051769	regulation of nitric-oxide synthase biosynthetic process	5.91664E-05
GO:0042742	defense response to bacterium	6.48121E-05
GO:0042737	drug catabolic process	0.000096515
GO:0001906	cell killing	0.00019549
GO:0006955	immune response	0.000230986
GO:0031424	keratinization	0.000310498
GO:0045721	negative regulation of gluconeogenesis	0.000367765
GO:0050896	response to stimulus	0.000569659
GO:0070989	oxidative demethylation	0.000630721
GO:0045818	negative regulation of glycogen catabolic process	0.000727769
GO:0009617	response to bacterium	0.000795299
GO:0009820	alkaloid metabolic process	0.000989003
GO:0042415	norepinephrine metabolic process	0.000989003
GO:0042738	exogenous drug catabolic process	0.000989003
<i>Hypomethylated genes in ATC</i>		
GO term ID	Term	Pvalue
GO:0031424	keratinization	2.375E-07
GO:0006955	immune response	1.16822E-05
GO:0006953	acute-phase response	1.29761E-05
GO:0030216	keratinocyte differentiation	0.000027967
GO:0031640	killing of cells of other organism	6.20737E-05
GO:0042742	defense response to bacterium	0.000104537
GO:0009913	epidermal cell differentiation	0.000113111
GO:0008228	opsonization	0.00013224
GO:0045087	innate immune response	0.000136202
GO:0001906	cell killing	0.000138789
GO:0050832	defense response to fungus	0.000254668
GO:0009595	detection of biotic stimulus	0.000495598
GO:0008544	epidermis development	0.000632648
GO:0006952	defense response	0.000797955
GO:0050776	regulation of immune response	0.000945417

Figure legends

Figure 1. Hierarchical clustering heatmap showing the DNA methylation patterns of autosomal probes in 2 normal thyroid samples, 8 thyroid primary tumors and 4 thyroid cancer cell lines. Whether the CpG site analyzed is associated to a CpG island (CGI) or not can clearly be distinguished.

Figure 2. Hierarchical clustering heatmap including all CpG dinucleotides with differential DNA methylation values (hypermethylated and hypomethylated) from each thyroid cancer subtype (A). Venn diagrams showing the number of differentially methylated CpG sites and genes in each thyroid cancer subtype and differentially methylated CpG sites and genes shared by the different subtypes (B). Hierarchical clustering heatmap including common hyper- and hypomethylated CpG sites in differentiated (left) and undifferentiated primary tumors (right) (C).

Figure 3. Box plots of microarray-based gene expression data including genes differentially expressed by thyroid cancer subtypes. In each thyroid cancer subtype differentially methylated genes (hyper- and hypomethylated) exhibited lower and higher expression levels respectively compared to normal tissues. P-values are shown.

Figure 4. Bar plots for each thyroid cancer subtype displaying the percentage of genes enriched for polycomb repressor complex 2 (upper panels) and for 3mK4H3 and 3mK27H3 (lower panels) in embryonic stem cells. (* p-value < 0.05, ** p-value < 0.01, *** p-value < 0.001).

Figure 5. Examples of PTC and FTC hypermethylated CpG sites in particular genes further validated by pyrosequencing. A schematic representation of the studied region and the methylation values from two representative primary tumors and normal samples are shown. The location of each CpG site is represented by vertical lines and the right angled arrow indicates the transcriptional start site (TSS). Analyzed region (blue line) and the CpG sites in the array (red box) are highlighted. Black depicts methylated CpG and white indicates unmethylated CpG.

Figure 6. Examples of MTC and ATC hypomethylated CpG sites in particular genes further validated by pyrosequencing. A schematic representation of the studied region and the methylation values from two representative primary tumors and normal samples are shown. The location of each CpG site is represented by vertical lines and the right angled arrow indicates the transcriptional start site (TSS). Analyzed region (blue line) and the CpG sites in the array (red box) are highlighted. Black depicts methylated CpG and white indicates unmethylated CpG.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Supplementary Figure 1

Supplementary Figure 1. Hierarchical clustering heatmap showing the methylation profiles of CpG sites of gender chromosomes (X and Y).

Supplementary Figure 2

Supplementary figure 2. Density plots showing no significant differences in average distance to TSS between hypermethylated (red line) and hypomethylated CpG sites (blue line). Graphic representations of hyper- and hypomethylated CpG sites for each subtype are shown both separately and all together (All). Dotted lines represent average values.

Supplementary Figure 3

Supplementary Figure 3. Bar diagrams showing the methylation array beta values of genes selected for pyrosequencing analysis.